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D.3.1 FIXLAB First Access Report

Lead Author: François Mirambet (CNRS – C2RMF)

**Co-authors: Rémi Petitcol (FSP), Quentin Lemasson (CNRS – C2RMF),
Florian Bourguignon (CNRS – C2RMF)**

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Authors (Partner)	CNRS – C2RMF		
Responsible Author	Name: François Mirambet	Partner: CNRS – C2RMF	

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Abstract

FIXLAB is a distributed platform composed of 23 stationary research infrastructures based in 12 European countries that gives access to more than 130 analytical techniques and the associated expertise. It provides transnational access to external researchers all across Europe that investigate major questions related to the materiality of Heritage artefacts (or samples) in terms of their genesis, manufacturing process, alterations, conservation and preservation, etc.

This first access report covers the activities carried out by FIXLAB from the start of the project to the 1st of July 2022. These activities include the initial work of building the FIXLAB access offer through the catalogue and its categories, the elaboration of a common access policy and selection criteria together with the MOLAB and ARCHLAB platforms, and the setting up of the FIXLAB helpdesk, and the creation of remote access opportunities. This report also analyses the results of the first three calls for access and their state of completion. This report is concluded with a work plan and some perspectives for the future of the platform.

Table of contents (page)

Document information: **2**

Abstract: **3**

Table of contents: **4**

List of figures and tables: **5**

Abbreviations: **6**

Narrative (technical) description: **7**

1. *Introduction: an unprecedented expansion of the FIXLAB platform: 7*
2. *Creating a new access process and opening new access modalities: 11*
3. *Results of the first access period (first three calls): 15*
4. *Conclusion: 28*

References **28**

List of figures and tables

Figure 1a: Table of FIXLAB providers per country

Figure 1b: repartition of the IPERION HS FIXLAB providers

Figure 2: repartition of the CHARISMA and the IPERION CH FIXLAB providers

Figure 3: repartition of the providers in four categories

Figure 4: Location of the research institutions

Table 1: The Peer Review Panel

Table 2: the FIXLAB projects selected

Table 3: the rejected projects

Table 4: the unfeasible projects

Table 5: List of completed projects

Table 6: Remaining access slots per provider

Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
FIXLAB	Fixed Laboratories
HS	Heritage Science
TNA	Transnational Access
PRP	Peer Review Panel

Narrative (technical) description

1. Introduction: an unprecedented expansion of the FIXLAB platform

1.1 From four providers across two countries to 23 providers in 12 countries

The main objective of FIXLAB is to provide heritage professionals with access to powerful analysis platforms to obtain information that can be decisive to face the challenges posed by cultural heritage.

Today FIXLAB offers a much wider range of analytical techniques to answer the questions of heritage stakeholders in the field of art history, manufacturing processes, conservation and restoration. Users have access to twenty-three research infrastructures spread over twelve European countries (figures 1a and 1b).

Figure 1a: Table of FIXLAB providers per country

Figure 1b: repartition of the IPERION HS FIXLAB providers

This set of facilities includes more than one hundred and thirty analysis techniques, which is far beyond the scope of previous European projects such as CHARISMA and IPERION CH (Figure 2). Compared to its predecessors, the IPERION HS FIXLAB collects a nearly complete range of Heritage Science techniques. This will provide high quality data on the different materials to be analyzed.

Figure 2: repartition of the CHARISMA and the IPERION CH FIXLAB providers

Moreover, each platform has teams of experts with different skill and background in the field of micro-analysis of artefacts to provide support to users and allows a wide range of scientific issues to be addressed. Some of them are also experienced in the field of heritage materials constituting the works: easel painting, graphic art, copper-based metals, ceramics and stones, glass, organic materials.

Heritage objects are most often made up of materials of very varied nature, which require very diverse analytical tools. From this point of view, the FIXLAB analytical platforms are perfectly adapted: they cover a wide range of scientific analysis domains that allow for the realization of very complete examinations.

Because of the large number (23) of trans-national access providers within FIXLAB, we have established four categories (Figure 3) to provide better orientation to FIXLAB users and to organize the FIXLAB Peer Review Panel:

- A. Large scientific instruments (Synchrotron, IBA, Neutrons, proteomics, C14, etc.);
- B. Specialised scientific platforms for cultural heritage (laser platform, tomography, etc.);
- C. Specialised scientific platforms for archaeology and palaeontology/palaeoanthropology;
- D. Specialised scientific platforms for restoration and preventive conservation.

Group	Category	Platforms
A	Ion Beam Analysis	AGLAE
		ATOMKI
	Synchrotron Techniques	SOLEIL
	Neutron Techniques	BNC
		MLZ
	Dating	INFN
Proteomics	HS OMICS	
B	Focused on Cultural Heritage	ITAM
		IQFR
		IPANEMA
		VU/GGL
		HML
		RAA
		HE
C	Focused on Archaeology, Palaeontology, and Palaeoanthropology	CEZA
		CENIEH
		AST RX
		INFN LNGS
		SciLifeLab
		BioArch
D	Focused on restoration and preventive conservation	UCL
		LNEC
		FORTH

Figure 3: repartition of the providers in four categories

It is important to note that these groups were set up to simplify the work of the Peer Review Panel and the general orientation of users. It does not preclude a provider from working on a given topic as long as it involves the tools listed in the catalogue and can be labeled as Heritage Science.

1.2A common access policy

A common access policy was drafted and adopted by the three TNA platforms of IPERION HS. This document covers the eligibility criteria, the selection procedure and access preparation, the conditions for the use of services (purpose of the research, applicable legislation and regulation, and cost), the user duties (notably in terms of acknowledgement, open data, IPR, security and insurance), and access limitations and force majeure. This final section was particularly important given the still ongoing COVID 19 pandemic.

In order to make sure that all users and potential users understand the main principles of this access policy, an abridged version was also created with 11 principles (<https://www.iperionhs.eu/iperion-hs-access-policy/>) and COVID 19 disclaimer was added to the website in the access section.

1.3A new catalogue of services

Given the unprecedented expansion of the FIXLAB platform in terms of its geographical distribution and more importantly in its analytical and scientific range (from the macroscopic to the atomic scale), creating the FIXLAB part of the catalogue of services proved to be an interesting challenge.

The definition of the final list of techniques and the association of these techniques to specific tools required a lot of discussion between the relevant providers, the FIXLAB management team and the Coordination Office. In practice, several difficulties emerged on the adoption of a common description of general techniques (i.e. what is PIXE, what are its fields of application, what materials it can analyze, etc.), and sometimes what constitutes a technique by itself. In some cases, it was decided to bundle less well-known techniques together in order to improve user readability.

This process was iterative and led to many updates of the catalogues based on meetings with the providers working in related fields (neutron techniques, ancient DNA, etc.). The categorization of techniques was tested in the first call (fall 2020) and improved in January 2021 for the opening of the second call.

The final main categories are the following: Ageing techniques, Biological Analysis, Conservation techniques and preparation methods, Dating, Environmental Parameters Measurements, Imaging (Multiscale and Multispectral), Ion Beam Analysis, Mass Spectrometries, Microscopies, Molecular Analysis, Molecular Spectroscopies, Neutron Techniques, Optical Spectroscopies, Physical Characterization, Thermal Characterization, and X-Ray Techniques.

A common application form was developed in parallel. This application form was inspired by the IPERION CH application form and includes changes or addition to better reflect the diversity of the access offer and the new possibility to apply for several FIXLAB facilities in one proposal. It also includes modular sections to better address the specificities of FIXLAB, MOLAB and ARCHLAB.

2. Creating a new access process and opening new access modalities

2.1 Helpdesk and feasibility check

Given the highly interdisciplinary nature of Heritage Science, the IPERION HS user base is composed of researchers coming from diverse disciplines. This implies that users are sometimes not acquainted with the techniques offered within FIXLAB, and many of them are not used to submitting proposals to access scientific equipment.

The IPERION HS helpdesk is structured in three main entry points for the users: the general user helpdesk (userhelpdesk@iperionhs.eu, run by CNR) for general queries, the FIXLAB Helpdesk (fixlabhelpdesk@atomki.hu, run by ATOMKI, assisted by CENIEH and RAA), and the facility contact persons (available for each tool or technique via the catalogue). Given the multiplicity of access points available to the potential users and the multiple forms that a contact with the help desk system can take, we cannot provide an exact percentage of proposals that followed a query to the helpdesk, but an analysis of the emails received and a feedback from providers indicate that this number is somewhere between 20% and 30%.

Once a proposal is submitted, it undergoes a feasibility assessment by the requested provider. This evaluation is a precondition for the proposal to be transferred to the FIXLAB Peer Review Panel for evaluation. The delay for this assessment is typically up to one week, although some providers have a much longer reply time, sometimes causing important delays in the peer reviewing process. This situation remains rare and often results from two situations: the contact point of the provider is unavailable (holidays, medical leave, etc.) and nobody else can perform the assessment in the facility, or, in large facilities, the local contact points have changed and are not well acquainted with the IPERION HS dashboard. Although it is impossible to prevent local force majeure events, the concerned access providers are aware of the issue and are actively trying to improve their internal processes.

Over the first three calls, 10 proposals were deemed completely unfeasible by the providers (or in some cases the FIXLAB management based on eligibility rules), which makes it below ten percent of the received proposals. Several projects that involved several providers were only deemed partially feasible and were sent for peer reviewing only for the feasible providers. We also have several examples of unfeasible being successfully resubmitted in a subsequent call.

2.2 The Peer Review Panel and selection criteria

The FIXLAB Peer Review Panel is composed of the following external experts. It is composed of 36 experts covering the wide range of analytical techniques and materials studied within FIXLAB. It was established at the beginning of the project based on names suggested by the providers. Because providers suggested on average three names for one FIXLAB PRP position, we can also benefit from a large basket of experts when the current PRP are not in position to evaluate proposals (not expert in the domain described in the proposal, conflict of interest, etc.).

Although this list is already long and diverse, several project proposals were addressing questions out the scope of expertise of the Peer Review Panel, and several Reviewers that previously agreed in writing to participate to a call evaluation eventually fail to reply to the coordination emails, causing major delays for some proposals to be evaluated. After speaking with concerned providers, it appears this shortage of experts or their lack of commitment is generalised in their field. This is why the current list is currently being revised together with the concerned providers. Eight of the least responsive experts are currently being replaced, and 10 experts are being provided with additional back-up experts.

Name	Position	Field	Institution	Group
Andreas Karydas	Director of research	IBA, X-ray fluorescence, Physics applied to Cultural Heritage	Demokritos	A
Lucio Calcagnile	Professor	IBA, non-destructive nuclear analysis, Physics applied to Cultural Heritage	Universita del Salento	A
János Dani	Deputy Director, Chief Archaeologist	Archeology, prehistory, near East, mediterranean	Déri Museum	A
Susanne Greiff	Head of Achaometry Research Departement	Archeology, history of techniques, glass, metallurgy, China	Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum	A
Francesco Grazi	Physicist	Ethnicity, Neolithic Archaeology, and Pottery (Archaeology).	CNR-IFAC	A
Katalin T. Biró	Archaeologist	Archaeometry, Prehistoric Archaeology	Hungarian National Museum	A
Maria Isabel Marques Dias	Geologist	archaeometry, geochemistry plus mineralogy, luminescence methods	Universidade De Lisboa	A
Carlos Cordeiro	Professor	Structural Mass Spectrometry, enzymology	Universidade de Lisboa	A
Daniela Comelli	Physicist	Photonics for health, food and cultural heritage	Politecnico di Milano	A
Dario Bernal Cassassola	Professor	Archeology, late roman pottery, ancient economies	University of Cadiz	A

Luca Bombardieri	Archaeologist	Archeology, bronze and iron age in Europe, Near East	University of Turin	A
Marco Martini	Professor	Material science, cultural heritage	University of Milano Bicocca	A
Massimiliano Ghinassi	Geologist	geosciences	University of Padua	A
Britta Schmutzler	Associate Professor	Conservation restoration, organic materials in archeology	Staatliche Akademie der Bildenden Künste Stgt	A
Matthias Heinzl	Head of Restauration Departement.	Metal (gold)/ archaeological restoration	Johannes Gutenberg Universität-Mainz	A
Anna LLUVERAS TENORIO	Chemist	Gas chromatographic/Mass Spectrometric procedures and Synchrotron Radiation, paintings	Università di Pisa Via	A
Laurence De VIGUERIE	Chemist	Renaissance, Paints, Colloid Chemistry, Soft Materials, Rheology, Material Characterization, Gelation	UPMC - Paris	A
Patricia WILS	Researcher	tomography, natural heritage	CNRS	A
Alexandra Livarda	Archaeologist	Landscape, environmental, and social archaeology	The Catalan Institute of Classical Archaeology	B
Tim Wess	Professor	Collagen, Fibrous Protein Structure, Cultural Heritage, Biopolymers	University of the Sunshine Coast	B
Javier Laserna	Professor	laser, Applied Spectroscopy, analytical chemistry	U. Malaga	B
Radka Sefcu	Conservation Scientist	Chemistry, paintings	National Gallery Prague	B
Thea Winther	Preservation specialist, Conservator, MSc	Archives, plastic, conservation	Swedish National Archives	B
Manfred Schreiner	Associate Professor	Corrosion Materials Chemistry Art XRD Analysis Cultural Heritage Spectroscopy Material Characterization Metals Spectrometry	Académie des Beaux-Arts de Vienne	B

Stephen Merkel	Researcher	Archaeometallurgy, and Conservation	Oxford and Bochum	B
Wolfgang Kautek	Head of the Physical chemistry department	Biochemistry, nanotechnology	University of Vienna	C
Rolf Quam	paleoanthropologist	evolutionary aspects of the temporal bone, mandibles and teeth in human fossils	Binghamton University	C
Vincent C. Pigott	prehistorian	Eurasia, South East Asia, prehistoric metallurgy	Museum of the University of Pennsylvania	C
Francesca Castorina	Associate Professor of Geochemistry	geochemical tracing, isotopic characterization methods	Università degli Studi di Roma "Sapienza"	C
Maeva Orliac	Researcher	evolutionary history of mammals, paleoneurology	Université de Montpellier	C
Carina Schlebusch	Evolutionary Biologist	genetics, population history of Africa, Organismal Biology	Uppsala University	C
Austin Nevin	Chemist and conservator	analysis of paintings and painting materials, optical and spectroscopic techniques applied to heritage	The Courtauld Institute of Conservation	D
Johann Nimmrichter	Physicist	conservation and restoration of monuments	Department for Conservation Federal Office for Care and Protection of Monuments in Austria	D
Violeta Lazic	Researcher	Remote Sensing Applied, Plasma Diagnostics, Spectroscopy Laser, Laser Ablation, Plasma Laser,	ENEA	D
José Delgado Rodrigues	Geologist	Characterisation of stone, Stone decay, degradation mechanisms	Free Lance Consultant	D
Yun Liu	Post-doctoral fellow	degradation of iron gall ink and historical paper	Smithsonian Museum Conservation Institute	D

Table 1: The Peer Review Panel

3. Results of the first access period (first three calls)

3.1 Selected projects

Table 2: the FIXLAB projects selected

Acronym	Title	Leader	User Leader country	Access provider	Call number
ARMOIRE	Analysis of raw material used for Roman MOSaic tesserae	Giuseppe Politi	Italy	AGLAE	1
ARTILE	Antwerp Renaissance TILES: supporting historical knowledge with Instrumental analysis	Geert Vandersnickt	Belgium	LNEC	1
ATTIA	Analysis of the distribution of Titanium oxide layer deposited on painting for self-cleaning and protective sake	Stefania Pasquale	Italy	AGLAE	1
CCCHRM	Characterization of Cellulosic Cultural Heritage Reference Materials –	Fenella France	United States	HML	1
CH_MPPM	Colour changes in Munch paintings and study of the artist's painting materials	Irina Sandu	Norway	HML, IPANEMA	1
CHAGRI	Non-invasive characterisation of grisaille paints on stained-glass windows	Marcia Vilarigues	Portugal	IQFR	1

ChaSAP	Characterization of stone tool Surface and sub-surface Alteration Processes during use	Antony Borel	Hungary	AGLAE	1
ChMoln	Attestations of Early Iron Age Chicken in SE Alps – understanding change, mobility and innovations	Borut Toskan	Slovenia	INFN, BioArch	1
ColourAs	The colour of Bronze Age arsenical copper: intended outcome or long-term change?	Marianne Moedlinger	Italy	RAA	1
DANAGAA	The dynamics of ancient networks in the Arabian Gulf through archaeometric and archaeological studies	Stefan Laursen	Denmark	AGLAE	1
DiODuCat - F	Discovering Old Dubrovnik Cathedral – FIXLAB	Suzana Damiani	Croatia	INFN, CENIEH	1
ECME Abu Rawash	Early Copper Metallurgy in Egypt: a case study of the material from Abu Rawash	Jiri Kmosek	Czech Republic	AGLAE	1
ESAM	Environmental Study of an Armoury Museum	Rahul Shukla	India	UCL	1
FINGERCHALC	Fingerprinting Chalcolithic artefacts from ditched enclosures	Rosa Marques	Portugal	BNC	1
FLORES	FLuorine content On Roman cremated bonES	Stephan Dubernet	France	ATOMKI	1
GEOCOMLES	Geochemical characterisation of the archaeological and geological colouring materials from the Lessini pre-Alpine massif (North-Eastern Italy)	Giorgia Sardelli	Italy	AGLAE	1

IVORIST	Provenance and circulation issues of pre-historic ivory and schist remarkable artefacts	Ana Luisa Rodrigues	Portugal	BNC	1
JMB-NCHT	Jewellery from the recent discovery in Mšec In Bohemia from the Great Migration Period : Quest for the Origin of the “New Childeric” treasure	Jaroslav Jirik	Czech Republic	AGLAE	1
LaMPaplas	Su pitture laser e plastiche moderne	Grazia De Cesare	Italy	FORTH	1
LionMan	non-invasive study of the lion man sculpture made of mammoth ivory	Kurt Wehrberger	Germany	AGLAE	1
MAILCOM 2021	The construction of Celtic mail armour	Alan Williams	United Kingdom	BNC	1
MAL-GLASS-ROM	A window in the chemistry of Roman glass: Study of Archaeological finds from MĂLĂIEȘTI, Romania (2nd century AD)	Roxana Bugoi	Romania	AGLAE	1
MeCaMi	MeCaMi: Metals in the Castle: Early Modern Materials for Objects of a Noble Residence and Military Stronghold in Middelburg-in-Flanders (Belgium, 15th-17th c.)	Lise Saussus	Belgium	AGLAE	1
MOSAICS	Elemental composition of glass mosaics tesserae: A non-destructive study by PGAA	Daniela Di Martino	Italy	BNC	1

NAARB	Multi-elemental characterization of Renaissance Bronze alloy fragments by means of Neutron Activation Analysis (NAA)	Francesco Cantini	Italy	MLZ	1
NeutronChert	Geochemical provenance studies with Neutron-NDT on chert tools from Upper Palaeolithic groups from Iland Iberia	Marta Sanchez de la Torre	Spain	MLZ	1
NurBronze	Neutron tomography analysis of morphological and microstructural features of four cast bronze statues from “Nuragic” Period of Sardinia	Francesco Grazzi	Italy	MLZ	1
RHINESR	Deciphering long-term river incision and early human occupation in the Middle Rhine Valley by Electron Spin Resonance dating	Melanie Bartz	Switzerland	CENIEH	1
ROMAN GLASS @ BLACK	Non-invasive compositional characterization of Roman glass finds from Black Sea coast archaeological sites	Roxana Bugoi	Romania	BNC	1
SIBILLA	Simultaneous Ion Beam Investigations for Lapis Lazuli provenance Analysis	Laura Guidorzi	Italy	AGLAE	1
SOOCA	Study Of OChre based pigment on Archaeological object from different sites for a possible provenance attribution	Giuseppe Politi	Italy	AGLAE	1
SpIDe	Specific Identification of Prehistoric Burnt Bones	Gregory Abrams	Belgium	HS OMICS	1

STEELENCE	Steel reference marks of historical German armours and swords revisualized through phase contrast neutron imaging	Francesco Grazzi	Italy	MLZ	1
T.HER.A	Traditional HERitage of the Aegean: Deciphering the use of “theran earth” in Therasia’ s building materials	Nikiforos Meimaroglou	Greece	LNEC	1
VACCAEANGLOSS	Ion beam analysis of ancient vaccaean glass beads	Joao Pinto	Spain	AGLAE	1
BRASS	Roman brass samples coming from ancient Mediolanum town: a PIXE investigation for the study of the production technology	Giulia Marcucci	Italy	AGLAE	2
Color-Bergs	Stone Ages colouring materials procurement strategies in southern african mountainous ranges	Guilhem Mauran	South Africa	AGLAE	2
COPPEREAST	Copper alloys quality in Eastern Central European late medieval large urban centres (Prague-Wroclaw): consumption and production strategies of craftsmen and consumers.	Jakub Sawicki	Czech Republic	AGLAE	2
EANFEM	Element analysis of non-ferrous metals from Medieval Bulgaria	Stela Doncheva	Bulgaria	ATOMKI	2
Egyptian Lapis Lazul	Provenance Analyses of Egyptian Lapis Lazuli objects	Judit Zoeldfoeldi	Germany	BNC	2

LaSi	Laser-assisted removal of lacquer from silver alloy objects; investigation for optimum parameters and assessment of the result	Charlotta Bylund Melin	Sweden	FORTH	2
MmKc	Meaningful materials in the khipu code: a multi-modal analysis	Lucrezia Milillo	United Kingdom	INFN, HML	2
OLYXRD	Hidden structures in the Greek oikos	Mara Schumacher	United Kingdom	SOLEIL	2
OSIRIS	Obsidian Identification in the Early Neolithic Radiating Island of Sardinia	Carlo Luglie	Italy	AGLAE	2
Shell POP	“Top-down” Shell Palaeoproteomics	Jorune Sakalauskaite	Denmark	HS OMICS	2
SIBILLA	Simultaneous Ion Beam Investigations for Lapis Lazuli provenance Analysis	Laura Guidorzi	Italy	AGLAE	2
AIAGM	An archaeometry investigation of ancient glass found in Malta: raw material, trade origin and deterioration processes	Matthew Grima	Malta	SOLEIL	3
CELLULO3D	Celluloid sunglasses: recognizing the degradation factors of 3D objects using high-res spectral imaging techniques	Artur Neves	Portugal	IPANEMA	3
CEMENTOmicS	Life history related organic compound modifications of archaeological dental remains	Martine Vercauteren	Belgium	HS OMICS	3

CHAGRI 2	Non-invasive characterisation of grisaille paints on stained-glass windows (2)	Marcia Vilarigues	Portugal	IQFR	3
CropDisperSW	Unravelling Crop Dispersal from southwest Asia	Laura Botigue	Spain	BioArch	3
DUV4Manuscripts	Quantification of the main components of medieval paints using synchrotron UV–VIS multispectral luminescence	Maria Joao Melo	Portugal	SOLEIL	3
FinCo	Finding Continuity in shell derived climate data	Niklas Hausmann	Germany	FORTH, BioArch	3
GEOCOMLES2	Geochemical characterisation of the archaeological and geological colouring materials from the Lessini pre-Alpine massif (North-Eastern Italy)	Giorgia Sardelli	Italy	AGLAE	3
IDeLA	Identifying Decorative Laminates	An Jacquemain	Belgium	HML	3
MELB	Mobility and Exchange at Ljubljansko barje and Trieste Karst: non-destructive analysis of Copper Age pottery	Elena Leghissa	Slovenia	BNC	3
MMM:kipu	Mapping Meaningful Materials: in the khipu code	Marei Hacke	Sweden	HE	3
SMELIBS	Stratigraphy of metals in heritage pollution crusts by LIBS	Paola Fermo	Italy	HML, AGLAE, IPANEMA	3
TANGLE	Tissue-specific ANalysis of Glycation for Lifespan Estimation	Ruairidh Macleod	United Kingdom	HS OMICS	3
UCSAEM	Uncovering of the copper sources in ancient Egyptian metallurgy	Jiri Kmosek	Czechia	CEZA	3

REMIXIS	Recontextualisation of ancient museum collections lacking of data. Unmasking an exceptional Mixtec mosaic mask through its material analysis.	Aline Huybrechts	Belgium	AGLAE, IPANEMA, HML	3
Rho-Glass	Rhodian Glass In pre- Roman times	Maria Kaparou	Athens	BNC	3

3.2 Rejected projects

Acronym	Title	Leader	User Leader country	Access provider	Call number
ABAGAR	Radiocarbon dating of carved wooden blocks for Abagar amulet rolls printing	Ines Vodopivec	Slovenia	INFN	1
AMSACHRONO	Anyama Middle Stone Age Chronology	Eslem Ben Arous	Germany	CENIEH	1
BAO	Bread as an Art Object	Jasna Jablan	Croatia	HML	1
CRO-N-PLIT	Chronology of Plitvice Lakes system, Croatia	Jadranka Baresic	Croatia	INFN, CEZA, CENIEH	1
LACeS_FIXLAB	Lipid analysis of Ancient Ceramics in South Asia_FIXLAB	Akshyeta Suryanarayan	France	HML	1
BisonSIHU	Analysis of Late Pleistocene and Holocene Bison fossils from Slovenia and Hungary	Lars Zver	Slovenia	INFN	2
Agox	Examination of silver surface species on silverpoint drawings	Markus Hofmann	Germany	SOLEIL, LNEC, HML	3

PIXEROM	Comparative PIXE and PIGE analysis of Romanian obsidian samples and obsidian artifacts from NE Great Hungarian Plain	Agnes Gal	Romania	ATOMKI	3
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Table 3: the rejected projects

3.3 Unfeasible projects

Acronym	Title	Leader	User Leader country	Access provider	Call number
BANDM	Bayesian Analysis Networks for Dynamic Media	Mark Ormsby	United States	UCL	1
AAA-Pi	Artificial accelerated ageing of a variety of handmade papers for their application to the conservation of Islamic manuscripts and associated works on paper	Amelie Couvrat Desvergnès	The Netherlands	RAA	2
ASTSR	Micro structure analysis of ancient silk textiles along the Silk Road	Jianlan Wang	China	AGLAE, SOLEIL	2
Renne-Provenance	Determination of the provenance of iron-rich coloring matter from petrological and geochemical characterization: the case study of “La grotte du Renne” artefacts (Arcy-sur-Cure)	Aurelie Chassin-De Kergommeaux	France	AGLAE	2

DiRect CesS	Dietary Reconstruction from Cesspits Sediments	Matthew Collins	United Kingdom	BioArch	3
MOCKED-UP	Mid-infrared mapping of Organic Compounds as Key Elements of Degradation in Unvarnished Paintings	Jan Dariusz Cutajar	Norway	IPANEMA	3
Ro.LEAD (Roman Lead)	Roman Lead artefacts from Roman Imperial Harbour (Portus Augusti) and city of Ancient Ostia: study of metal provenance and characterization of the metal finds	Emanuela Spagnoli	Italy	LNGS	3
Royal wood coffin	3D Insight into Pharoanic Royal wood coffin and Pharoanic Wooden Statue treated by different Nano-Consolidation Systems.	Dina Atwa Khalil	Egypt	AST-RX	3
ICTI	The impact of conservation treatments on isotope analysis	Lu Allington-Jones	United Kingdom	CEZA	4
NICER	Neutron-based Imaging CERamic Residues	Michael Buckley	United Kingdom	BNC	4
SPINOSO	Study of Particulate matter in INdoor air and of powder deposit On painted surface of wooden statues of Santuario della Beata Vergine dei Miracoli of Saronno (VA) – Italy.	Giuseppe Politi	Italy	AGLAE	4

Table 4: the unfeasible projects

3.4 Location of the research institutions requesting FIXLAB access

Figure 4: Location of the research institutions

23 countries have sent proposals for access to the different fixlab platforms. The most numerous requests come from Italy, Belgium and Portugal. We also have access requests from countries outside Europe such as the United States, India, and South Africa. Non-European countries are involved in proposals coordinated by users from the ERA

The main scientific topics addressed in the proposals are:

- Study of the “manufacturing processes” -> know-how of the artists and the craftsmen, as well as on the choice, the source and the commercial circulation of the natural or synthetic materials used. (Keywords: Neolithic/Palaeolithic, Archeometry, Origin, Dating, Composition, Characterization)
- -Study of degradation phenomena of works of art -> estimate in a more reliable way the risks incurred by these materials in order to define a coherent policy as regards conservation. (Keywords: Pollution, Degradation, Conservation)

In addition, the most studied materials are: Pottery, Glass Metal, Pigments, Protein and Ceramic

3.5 List of completed projects:

Acronym	Access provider	Completion Date	User Report Submitted	Call Number
ARMOIRE	AGLAE	31/01/2021	No	1
ARTILE	LNEC	29/01/2021	No	1
ATTIA	AGLAE	31/01/2021	No	1
CHAGRI	IQFR	26/01/2021	No	1
ChaSAP	AGLAE	21/01/2021	Yes	1
FLORES	ATOMKI	31/01/2021	No	1
GEOCOMLES	AGLAE	18/12/2020	No	1
JMB-NCHT	AGLAE	18/01/2021	No	1
LionMan	AGLAE	29/01/2021	No	1
MAILCOM 2021	BNC	08/01/2021	No	1
MAL-GLASS-ROM	AGLAE	15/12/2020	Yes	1
MECAMI	AGLAE	28/01/2021	Yes	1
MOSAICS	BNC	30/01/2021	No	1
SIBILLA	AGLAE	31/01/2021	Yes	1
SOOCA	AGLAE	29/01/2021	No	1
T.HER.A	LNEC	17/01/2022	Yes	1
VACCAEANGLOSS	AGLAE	27/01/2021	No	1
COPPEREAST	AGLAE	30/06/2021	No	2
EANFEM	ATOMKI	07/07/2021	No	2
Lasi	FORTH	30/06/2021	No	2
OSIRIS	AGLAE	30/06/2021	No	2
CHAGRI 2	IQFR	29/11/2021	No	3

Table 5: List of completed projects

As this table show, only 22 out of the 81 proposals granted in the first three calls were completed carried out by the providers. There are three main reasons why there is such a delay in access delivery to users:

- First, and by far the most important reason, the COVID 19 pandemic has severely disrupted the facilities' work plans. In almost all cases, the facilities were closed for prolonged period of times and had to first deal with the "backlog" of activities canceled in 2020 and some of 2021 before scheduling IPERION HS transnational access. The new remote access options promoted by FIXLAB were sometimes useful to circumvent travel limitations or hazards, but did nothing to alleviate the backlog.
- Second, many FIXLAB providers had little to no experience in providing structured transnational access before this project. Setting up administrative procedures, and more generally local access protocols, took time. This is easily observable in the table above:

out of 22 completed projects, only 5 were performed by facilities that did not provide transnational access before IPERION HS. All the others were performed by facilities involved in IPERION CH and CHARISMA. We expect this issue to gradually disappear in the lifetime of the project.

- Some providers are not reporting the completed access on the IPERION HS dashboard, meaning that some projects were carried out or are almost completed at the time of this access report, but they do not appear yet in the list. This is a minor issue that will be solved before the next periodic reporting.

3.6 Remaining access slots per provider:

Provider	Granted call 1	Granted call 2	Granted call 3	Requested call 4	TOTAL	Completion rate (requested)
INFN FI	10	6	0	0	16	18%
MLZ	18	0	0	5	23	53%
AGLAE	54,5	21	6	10	91,5	76%
SOLEIL	0	3	8	0	11	63%
HS OMICS	15	10	15	5	45	188%
ATOMKI	5	5	0	0	10	13%
BNC	23	5	10	5	43	50%
ITAM	0	0	0	0	0	0%
IQFR	5	0	5	0	10	33%
IPANEMA	5	0	8	0	13	29%
VU	0	0	0	0	0	0%
RAA	5	0	0	0	5	100%
HML	7	6	6	10	29	193%
HML	0	0	3	0	3	38%
INFN GS	0	0	0	0	0	0%
CEZA	0	0	8	0	8	67%
CENIEH	11	0	0	18	29	145%
MNHN	0	0	0	0	0	0%
SciLifeLab	0	0	0	5	5	33%
BioArCh	5	0	10	9	24	57%
FORTH	5	3	10	0	18	36%
LNEC	12	0	0	0	12	30%
UCL	16	0	0	0	16	200%
TOTAL	196,5	59	89	67	411,5	52%

Table 6: Remaining access slots per provider

The table above shows the completion rate of the commitment of each infrastructure to FIXLAB based on their declaration in Grant Agreement (expressed in days of 8 hours). The overall completion rate, including all the requested days in the fourth call (some may not be pass the PRP

evaluation), is 52%. This is below the 64% target that we should have met in the fourth call, but could be balanced by the next calls.

So far there are very significant discrepancies in the amount requests the providers receive, which will likely require a reallocation of funds towards the facilities in very high demand.

4. Conclusion

Today, IPERION6HS FIXLAB provides access to excellent large-scale facilities with more than one hundred and thirty analysis techniques. The most direct scientific impact of Fixlab is to give through access to new powerful instruments, methods and techniques for heritage interpretation, documentation, conservation and treatment.

This new and more diversified offer makes the management of the platform more complicated. The user's community need more support because some of them are less experienced and do not always have a good knowledge of the potential of the available analytical tools. Contact with the helpdesk is greatly encouraged through the website and webinars. It is also recommended that user seek advice, from the scientists responsible for the platform, on the technical and instrumental aspects of the proposal before submitting it. The FIXLAB management team must provide more guidance on how to write a proposal for experiment which will stand a good chance of being approved.

In order to improve the proposal evaluation process, we need to take into account the comments feedback from the different PRPs reviewer In the proposal evaluation process, we have encountered some issues requiring additional information and an enhanced communication. Moreover, the shortage of experts or their lack of commitment is generalised for some specific field. This is why the current list is currently being revised together with the concerned providers.

Regarding the completion rate the examination of the data collected in the table X reveals that the value of 52% is slightly below the expected rate after the fourth call. However, there are very significant differences between the platforms that need to be analysed for the future implementation of the FIXLAB platform in E-RIHS. It is essential to enable by an updated access policy and catalogue to include a remote access provision for FIXLAB facilities

According to this first assessment, it is important to foresee an extension of the project in order to reach the objectives set for a number of platforms.

References

<https://www.iperionhs.eu/iperion-hs-access-policy/>

<https://www.iperionhs.eu/fixlab/>